

“TEACHING WRITING IN JUNIOR CLASSES”

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Beshariq tuman 1-son kasb-hunar maktabi Ingliz tili fani o'qituvchisi

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ANNOTATION

INTRODUCTION

In the process of teaching, teachers always unconsciously create a variety of situations for students. Most Chinese students lack English learning environment, so it is necessary for teachers to use situational teaching method. However, in the actual junior school English writing teaching process, most teachers use the traditional jug-and-mug teaching method, which leads teachers to ignore the dominant position of students' learning, their learning interest and motivation to a certain extent. The paper tries to find the ways that teach students in junior English writing based on Situational Teaching Method. Despite there are some the shortcomings of this study, the author still hopes that this study will be helpful to the further study of situational teaching method.

Writing is one of the predominant language skills in teaching English to ESL and EFL students in all educational levels, notably junior high school students.

Key words: situational teaching method, using multimedia, language acquisition, challenges in teaching junior classes,

The Definition of Situational Teaching Method

In spite of the controversies on language learning processes, there is the underlying fact that the main practical objective of teaching a language is to enable the learners to use it. That is, to know to what real-life situations each particular form of the target language corresponds.

Acquiring linguistic data is not sufficient because the scene is not a linguistic one, as it has to do with people, objects and events which are present at the moment of communication. In this respect Halliday remarks that “*when we acquire our primary language, we do so by learning how to behave in situations, not by learning rules about what to say*”

Language Acquisition Theory

Language acquisition is the process of learning to communicate effectively and meaningfully in a target language. There are four main theories: linguistic learning, behaviorist, cognitive learning, and interactionist. All theories have strengths and weaknesses.

Krashen hypothesizes that second language acquisition is very similar to the process children use when acquiring their first language. It requires meaningful interaction in the new language--natural communication--in which speakers are concerned with the messages they are conveying and understanding, not with the grammatical form of the language. According to Krashen, error correction and explicit teaching of rules are not important in language acquisition. Rather, students learn best when they are focusing on the purpose of

communicating, not the form of the language. Native speakers of a language, when interacting with nonnative speakers, naturally modify their speech into shorter, less complex sentences to help second language learners understand. In the literature, this type of language is commonly referred to as “foreigner talk.” Mothers also naturally modify their speech into shorter, less complex sentences, using pitch and intonation to help their babies learn their first language. In the literature, this type of language is commonly referred to as “motherese.” Modifications of language that occur during foreigner talk and motherese are thought to help the acquisition process, because language is being made more comprehensible to the learner. Krashen is most widely known for his "comprehensible input" hypothesis, which suggests that learners acquire language by taking in and understanding language that is "just beyond" their current level of competence. Krashen defines comprehensible input as ‘i+1’, where ‘I’ is the current level of proficiency and ‘+1’ is the level of proficiency just beyond the learner’s current level. As evidence of “comprehensible input”, Krashen points to examples of “foreigner talk” and “motherese” as being instances of input that is slightly beyond the learner’s current level of competence.

Using Multimedia to Create Situations

Multimedia refers to a combination of different media (such as audio, video and text) that can be used in education. For example, you might use film clips from movies or TV shows to teach your students about history; alternatively, if they were studying science then some images related to the topic would work well too.

The Benefits of Multimedia Education

The field of education is changing rapidly. The old days of schools with isolated AV departments and outdated TVs are long gone -- the use of modern multimedia within the education sector has accelerated in recent years and is set for continued expansion in the future.

In general, multimedia is the combination of visual and audio representations. These representations could include elements of text, graphic arts, sound, animation, and video. However, multimedia is restricted in systems where information is digitized and processed by a computer. Interactive multimedia and hypermedia consist of multimedia applications in which the user has a more active role.

Teachers primarily require access to learning resources, which support concept development to meet the individual learning needs of their students. By using multimedia technology, educators can offer new methods of learning that can take place in schools or at home. Granting teachers access to multimedia learning resources, which support constructive concept development, allows them to focus on facilitating learning while working with individual students. And extending the use of multimedia learning resources to the home represents an opportunity to improve distance learning.

The Challenges of Teaching English Writing to Junior High School Students

Students’ poor English grammatical competence

Based on the interview results, the researcher identified that teachers faced assorted challenges when teaching writing to junior high school students. One of them was generated from their English grammatical competence, as indicated by one of the participants (participant 2) as follows:

Excerpt 1

P2 “One of the challenges of teaching writing is due to how the way they write. Commonly, they applied spoken language to written in English. For instance, when I said “the word division” of a sentence, for example, “I will go to school by motorcycle” and I requested them to write it, they encountered obstacles to write. This may be caused by their difficulties to understand the sentence structure in English. Moreover, the participant argues that the students have difficulties in grammatical competences. They were difficulties in understanding the structure to write their ideas in written form. Then, the participant said that the most difficulties in teaching writing were teaching the structure such as they were difficulties to change the tenses when writing. In English, there are past tense, present tense, future, present continuous tense (study, studies, studied, studying), students encounter difficulties to apply the tenses.”

To sum up, using Situational Teaching Method in writing teaching can produce the connection between teaching content and students’ sensory experience, which can stimulate students’ enthusiasm for learning and is conducive to cultivating students’ interests in writing and improving their writing skills, optimizing the teaching effect and improving students’ writing ability.

The study aimed at depicting the challenges and solutions in teaching English writing to junior school students